

THE EFFECT OF CUSTOMER INCIVILITY ON WORK ENGAGEMENT, MODERATED BY SELF-EFFICACY (A Study at Prama Sanur Beach Hotel, Bali)

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ABSTRACT

The hospitality industry is characterised by roles involving a high intensity of service interactions; consequently, employees' psychological engagement in performing their job roles is a crucial factor in maintaining service quality, as reflected in their level of work engagement. This study aims to analyse the effect of customer incivility on work engagement, with self-efficacy serving as a moderating variable. Testing the job demands–resources theory, this study employs a quantitative approach with a causal design. The study population comprises all frontline employees at Hotel Prama Sanur Beach Bali, selected via saturation sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analysed using Structural Equation Modelling – Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) WarpPLS. The results indicate that customer incivility has a significant negative effect on work engagement. Self-efficacy was found to mitigate the negative impact of customer incivility on work engagement. These findings underscore the importance of strengthening self-efficacy as a personal resource to maintain employee work engagement when facing the emotional demands of the job.

Keywords: customer incivility, work engagement, self-efficacy.

ABSTRACT

The hospitality industry is characterised by roles involving a high intensity of service interactions; consequently, employees' psychological engagement in performing their job roles is a crucial factor in maintaining service quality, as reflected in their level of work engagement. This study aims to analyse the influence of customer incivility on work engagement, with self-efficacy acting as a moderating variable. Testing the job demands–resources theory, this study employs a quantitative approach with a causal design. The study population comprises all frontline staff at Hotel Prama Sanur Beach Bali, selected via saturation sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analysed using Structural Equation Modelling – Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) WarpPLS. The results indicate that customer incivility has a significant negative effect on work engagement. Self-efficacy was found to mitigate the negative impact of customer incivility on work engagement. These findings underscore the importance of strengthening self-efficacy as a personal resource to maintain employees' work engagement when facing the emotional demands of their jobs.

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Introduction

The hospitality industry, as a service sector centred on *hospitality*, faces complex operational dynamics and is heavily reliant on the quality of direct interactions between frontline staff and guests. *Frontline* staff in the hospitality industry demonstrate levels of *work engagement* that tend to be suboptimal when performing services that demand intensive, empathetic, swift, and precise interaction in accordance with company standards. Operational pressures, such as fluctuations in occupancy rates, service waiting times, operational disruptions, and demands for compliance with quality standards, increase staff workload and emotional demands in delivering friendly, accurate, and error-free service.

Such working conditions diminish employees' energy, dedication and engagement in their work—key dimensions of *work engagement*—thereby hindering their ability to maintain consistent service performance (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002). Frontline staff in a hotel work environment face complex and high-intensity service situations, particularly during the check-in process and when handling complaints, which deplete emotional resources, increase work-related stress, and trigger emotional exhaustion, ultimately reducing employees' levels of *work engagement* in carrying out their duties and responsibilities optimally (Hur *et al.*, 2023). *Work engagement* is a crucial positive psychological state for hospitality employees as it enables them to maintain sustained vitality, commitment, and focus at work, which ultimately determines the quality of service interactions and customer satisfaction (Karatepe, 2013).

A preliminary study involving interviews with 10 *frontline* staff at the Prama Sanur Beach Hotel in Bali revealed situational and fluctuating issues regarding *work engagement*. The interview results showed that the majority of staff experienced a temporary decline in motivation and focus after dealing with guests who behaved rudely, such as speaking in a raised voice, making repeated complaints, and adopting a demeaning attitude towards staff. The majority of employees stated that such incidents reduced their concentration at work and led to a tendency to work merely to complete tasks without optimal emotional engagement. *Frontline* staff retained a sense of pride in their work, yet their level of enthusiasm tended to decline in high-pressure service situations. Working conditions further undermined *work engagement* when workloads were unbalanced, service procedures were unclear, and managerial support was inconsistent.

This situation triggers emotional exhaustion, which has a direct impact on a decline in *work engagement*. Employees are able to restore *their work engagement* when they have clarity regarding work resources, receive support from colleagues and supervisors, and possess good communication skills following an incident. Organisational and *interpersonal* support enables employees to maintain their professionalism, ensuring that the quality of service provided to guests remains optimal.

Work engagement is a key issue in human resource management within the *hospitality* sector. Employees with high levels of *work engagement* tend to demonstrate

consistent enthusiasm, dedication to their work, and full involvement in organisational activities. However, negative interactions with customers in the form of *customer incivility* have the potential to reduce work engagement (Sliter et al., 2012).

The *Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Theory* explains that job characteristics consist of *job demands*—which require physical, cognitive and emotional effort—and *job resources*, which help employees meet these demands and maintain work motivation, thereby shaping their level of *work engagement* (Demerouti et al., 2001). In the hospitality industry, *customer incivility* acts as an emotional *job demand* that increases psychological pressure, as employees must allocate additional energy to control their emotions and maintain service quality, which has the potential to reduce *work engagement*; conversely, *self-efficacy* functions as a *personal resource* that strengthens employees' belief in their ability to manage job demands, thereby enabling employees to maintain optimal work focus, emotional control, and work engagement. The JD-R framework views *self-efficacy* as a buffering mechanism that mitigates the negative impact of *customer incivility* on *work engagement*, particularly in high-intensity service environments.

Customer incivility is a form of aggression that is non-physical but has a significant psychological impact on employees, particularly those on the front line. This behaviour can take the form of an unpleasant tone of voice, a lack of respect for staff time and effort, or even the use of abusive language that disrupts the emotional balance of the workforce (Andersson & Pearson, 1999) and (Farisi, S., et al., 2024).

Customer incivility generally arises in busy service situations such as *check-in/check-out* procedures, complaint handling, and breakfast queues. This behaviour manifests as disrespectful language, demands to be served immediately without regard for the queue, and comments that undermine staff professionalism. Employees and *supervisors* report that such situations are emotionally draining, dampen morale, and, if repeated, can undermine *work engagement* and service quality. They also linked *incivility* to misalignment of information, perceived unfairness of policies, language barriers, and work pressure, whilst emphasising the importance of managerial support, inter-departmental coordination, and a mutually respectful work environment to minimise the negative impact on the well-being and performance of *frontline staff*.

Self-efficacy is identified as a moderating variable because an individual's belief in their own abilities determines how they assess, respond to and manage work-related stress arising from the service environment. Interview findings indicate that *frontline* staff with high levels of *self-efficacy* are able to control their emotions, maintain their focus on work and make more adaptive service decisions, even when faced with rude behaviour from guests.

Employees with low *self-efficacy* tend to experience self-doubt, emotional exhaustion and reduced work engagement after dealing with serious complaints or excessive demands. These differences in self-efficacy levels indicate that *self-efficacy* influences the strength of the relationship between *customer incivility* and *work engagement*. High *self-efficacy* acts as a psychological resource that mitigates the negative

impact of customer incivility on *work engagement*, whilst low *self-efficacy* amplifies this negative impact.

Empirical research also indicates that negative customer interactions can reduce *self-efficacy* and service performance; however, this effect is weaker among employees with high *self-efficacy* (Hur *et al.*, 2022; Kim *et al.*, 2025). The inclusion of *self-efficacy* as a moderating variable has a strong theoretical and empirical basis for explaining variations in *frontline* employees' responses to *customer incivility* and its implications for *work engagement* within the hospitality industry.

Research by Jang *et al.* (2020) shows that *customer incivility* has a negative impact on employees' *work engagement*. This is due to increased emotional stress, which depletes employees' psychological resources, thereby reducing their enthusiasm and dedication at work. Another study conducted by Wang and Chen (2020) found that *customer incivility* significantly reduces employees' *work engagement* and job performance.

Al Halbusi *et al.* (2023) investigated the role of *self-efficacy* as a moderator of the relationship between psychological factors and *work engagement* among employees at five-star hotels in Iraq. The results of the study indicate that when employees possess high *self-efficacy*, this can mitigate the impact of *customer incivility* on *work engagement*. These findings suggest that *self-efficacy* serves to strengthen *work engagement* in a service context, thereby supporting the hypothesis that *self-efficacy* can also act as a psychological buffer when employees face *customer incivility*.

Furthermore, Alqhaiwi *et al.* (2024) reveal that incivility tends to be contagious in hotel environments, meaning that *customer incivility* can elicit similar behaviour from staff and create a negative cycle in the workplace. This cycle depletes psychological energy, increases work-related stress, and ultimately reduces *work engagement*, although the impact is less pronounced on individuals who possess high self-awareness and are able to manage negative emotions. Boukis *et al.* (2023) add that *customer incivility* can be perceived as a threat to the professional identity of *frontline* staff, which triggers role stress and reduces the tendency to help others, making *self-efficacy* an important personal resource for maintaining *work engagement*.

Employees with high *self-efficacy* are better able to regulate their emotions, maintain appropriate assertiveness, and remain focused on their tasks, thereby sustaining their *work engagement* even when faced with *customer incivility* (Shao & Skarlicki, 2021; Lin *et al.*, 2023). However, studies specifically examining the role of *self-efficacy* as a moderator of the relationship between *customer incivility* and *work engagement* in the Indonesian hospitality sector remain limited, even though a work culture that emphasises politeness and high power distance has the potential to cause employees to suppress their discomfort. This situation can lead to hidden stress that ultimately disrupts *work engagement*, making the strengthening of *self-efficacy* crucial for supporting employees' psychological resilience.

Based on the theoretical understanding that *customer incivility* can reduce *frontline* staff's *work engagement*, and given that such situations frequently occur in day-to-day

service operations, a more focused empirical analysis is required to understand its actual impact. More targeted research is required to systematically test the relationships between these variables and to obtain a more comprehensive picture within the context of service provision. The Prama Sanur Beach Hotel in Bali was selected as the research location due to its high level of interaction with guests and the suspected variation in *work engagement* levels amongst *frontline* staff.

This study aims to analyse the relationship between *customer incivility* and *work engagement* among *frontline* staff at the Prama Sanur Beach Hotel in Bali, and to examine the moderating role of *self-efficacy* in the relationship between *customer incivility* and *work engagement*.

Research Method

This study employs a quantitative approach as data is collected in numerical form. This is a causal-associative study, designed to identify the cause-and-effect relationship between one variable and another. The variables in this study are *work engagement* (Y) as the dependent variable, *customer incivility* (X) as the independent variable, and *self-efficacy* (M) as the moderator variable. The data collected for each variable will subsequently be analysed to address the research questions and examine the relationships between the variables in this study.

Results and Discussion

The Effect of Customer Incivility on Work Engagement

The results of this study indicate that *customer incivility* has a significant negative impact on employees' *work engagement*; in other words, the higher the intensity of rude, demeaning or disrespectful behaviour from customers, the lower the level of employees' work engagement. This decline is reflected across all dimensions of *work engagement*: a decrease in energy and mental resilience, a weakening of enthusiasm and the sense of meaning in work, and a reduction in the ability to immerse oneself and focus fully on the task at hand. These findings suggest that negative interpersonal interactions have a broad and lasting psychological impact on the work engagement of *frontline* staff.

From the perspective of the *Job Demands–Resources* (JD-R) Model, *customer incivility* can be classified as a *hindrance job demand*—that is, a work demand that not only drains emotional energy but also hinders the achievement of work goals and the motivational processes of employees (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Unlike *challenge demands*, which can still stimulate growth, *customer incivility* tends to be perceived as an unproductive *stressor* because it arises beyond the employee's control and is often not accompanied by organisational protective mechanisms. Consequently, these recurring emotional demands deplete employees' psychological resources and trigger a process of exhaustion that leads to a decline in *work engagement*.

The results of this study are consistent with recent empirical findings and align with the *Job Demands–Resources* (JD-R) theoretical framework proposed by Bakker and

Demerouti (2017). *Customer incivility* can be understood as a social job demand that depletes psychological resources, thereby hindering the emergence of optimal working conditions for employees. *Work engagement* itself is defined as a positive psychological state characterised by *vigour*, *dedication*, and *absorption* (Schaufeli et al., 2002), which is highly dependent on the balance between job demands and the availability of resources.

The findings of this study reinforce the empirical evidence that *customer incivility* significantly reduces *work engagement* among employees in the service and hospitality sectors. Early studies by Morrow et al. (2011) and Sliter et al. (2012) have shown that rude behaviour from customers increases work-related stress and emotional exhaustion, which ultimately has a negative impact on employees' work attitudes and engagement. More recent longitudinal evidence was presented by Hur et al. (2022) through a *diary study* approach, which showed that experiencing *customer incivility* on a single working day not only reduced *vigour* and *dedication* on the same day, but also had a lasting impact on reduced *work engagement* the following day through increased *emotional exhaustion*.

Boukris et al. (2023) assert that *customer incivility* is perceived as a threat to the professional identity of *frontline* staff. This threat triggers psychological withdrawal, which in turn undermines *dedication* and *absorption*. These findings are consistent with those of Wang and Chen (2020) and Guo et al. (2022), who emphasise that negative customer interactions undermine the meaning of work and a sense of ownership of the service role, thereby eroding work engagement over time.

Research in the Asian context also supports these findings. Shahzad et al. (2023) and Gustiawan et al. (2023) found that *customer incivility* significantly increases emotional strain and affective exhaustion among hotel staff, leading to a decline in *vigour* and *dedication*. A study by Wisesa and Rahyuda (2024) in the Indonesian hospitality sector indicates that *customer incivility* acts as a primary trigger for reduced *work engagement*, particularly among *frontline* staff who experience high levels of customer interaction. These findings suggest that the impact of *customer incivility* is cross-cultural and relevant in the context of developing countries.

The systemic impact of *customer incivility* has also been highlighted by Kuriakose et al. (2023) and Alqhaiwi et al. (2024), who found that rude customer behaviour can trigger a negative cycle—manifesting as increased *incivility* amongst employees. This cycle exacerbates emotional exhaustion, reduces *vigour* and *absorption*, and creates an increasingly unproductive working environment. *Customer incivility* not only affects those directly exposed to it, but also undermines the organisation's overall psychosocial climate.

This situation becomes increasingly critical for *frontline* staff who are required to perform intensive *emotional labour*. Li and Shaffer (2024) and Rout (2025) demonstrate that *emotional labour* triggered by *customer incivility* reduces *dedication* and *absorption*, as employees lose a sense of authenticity and intrinsic meaning in their work. If this situation persists without any recovery of psychological resources, the decline in *work engagement* tends to become chronic, as explained in the *health impairment process* mechanism within the JD-R model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017).

The findings of this study have important implications for organisations in the service and hospitality sectors. *Customer incivility* needs to be understood as part of the psychosocial work environment, not merely as an individual risk to employees. Research by Agina (2025) indicates that strong organisational support through employee protection policies, clear boundaries regarding acceptable customer behaviour, training in handling problematic customers, and consistent *supervisory* support can mitigate the tendency towards *disengagement* and prevent the emergence of service sabotage behaviour resulting from *incivility*.

This discussion confirms that *customer incivility* is a destructive *job demand* that has a significant impact on reducing employees' *work engagement*. The consistency of these findings with previous studies reinforces the argument that managing customer interactions in a more humane and sustainable manner is a key prerequisite for maintaining work engagement and service quality in the long term.

The Moderating Role of Self-Efficacy in the Effect of Customer Incivility on Work Engagement

Hypothesis 2 in this study states that *self-efficacy* moderates the effect of *customer incivility* on *work engagement*. The results of the structural equation modelling using WarpPLS 7.0 indicate that the interaction path coefficient is 0.115 with a p-value of 0.072. These values suggest that the moderating effect of *self-efficacy* is not statistically significant; therefore, Hypothesis 2 is not empirically supported.

The findings of this study indicate that an individual's level of self-efficacy does not mitigate or enhance the negative impact of *customer incivility* on *work engagement*. Employees with high *self-efficacy* still experience a decline in work engagement when faced with customers who are rude, demeaning, or verbally aggressive. This finding suggests that *self-efficacy* does not function as a buffering mechanism in the relationship between interpersonal stressors and work engagement in the context of this study.

The *Job Demands–Resources (JD-R) Model* classifies *self-efficacy* as a *personal resource* that theoretically plays a role in enhancing intrinsic motivation and maintaining *work engagement* when individuals face job demands (Bakker & Demerouti, 2023). The findings of this study indicate that the effectiveness of *personal resources* is highly dependent on the characteristics of the job demands faced. A study by Boukis *et al.* (2023) confirms that *customer incivility* is perceived as a threat to the professional identity of service employees, thereby triggering intense emotional reactions and depleting psychological resources. Research by Shahzad *et al.* (2023) also demonstrates that rude customer behaviour significantly reduces *work engagement* through increased emotional exhaustion.

These empirical findings reinforce the argument that not *all job demands* can be effectively offset by *personal resources*. *Customer incivility*, as a demeaning socio-emotional demand, tends to undermine an individual's self-esteem and identity, thereby reducing the capacity of *self-efficacy* to function as a psychological buffer. This explains why self-

confidence alone is insufficient to maintain levels of job engagement when stressors are personal in nature and threaten one's dignity.

Organisational contextual factors may also help explain the lack of significance of this moderating effect. A service sector work environment with strict service standards limits employees' freedom to express emotions or respond assertively to customer behaviour. Recent research on emotional regulation in the service sector indicates that high demands for emotional management can weaken the positive influence of *personal resources* on work well-being (Kim et al., 2022). This situation prevents *self-efficacy* from being expressed optimally, as employees' responses are constrained by organisational rules and service expectations.

The overall findings of this study make an empirical contribution by demonstrating that *self-efficacy* does not always function as a moderator in the relationship between *interpersonal stressors* and *work engagement*. The effectiveness of *personal resources* has been shown to depend heavily on the intensity and characteristics of work demands, as well as the contextual support available. This finding enriches the literature on human resource management and organisational behaviour by emphasising the importance of a combination of personal resources and systematic organisational support in maintaining the sustainability of *work engagement*.

Implications of the Research Findings

Theoretically, this study has implications for the development of human resource management research, particularly in relation to *customer incivility*, *work engagement*, and *self-efficacy*. The findings of this study reinforce the *Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory*, which explains that *job demands* and *job resources* not only have a direct impact on employees, but also influence one another in explaining the dynamics of work engagement. The results indicate that *customer incivility*, as an additional *job demand*, has a significant negative effect on the *work engagement* of *frontline* staff, whilst *self-efficacy* was not found to significantly mitigate this effect.

In practical terms, the findings of this study may serve as a basis for consideration by the Prama Sanur Beach Bali Hotel and other accommodation providers in maintaining and enhancing the *work engagement* of *frontline* staff when faced with additional *job demands* such as *customer incivility*. Based on the descriptive analysis, *frontline* staff frequently experience *customer incivility*, particularly in the form of rude calls from guests seeking attention. This situation has the potential to reduce motivation and service quality, which may ultimately lead to guest complaints. *Frontline* staff exhibit a relatively strong level of *work engagement*, which supports their work ethic and performance; however, their perceived work energy remains at a moderate level, meaning service delivery tends to be standardised without extra effort. Furthermore, *frontline* staff possess moderate levels of *self-efficacy*, enabling them to feel confident and capable of adapting to meet guest needs; however, this level of confidence has not yet been sufficient to significantly mitigate the negative impact of *customer incivility* on *work engagement*.

Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations. Firstly, the use of a *cross-sectional* design limits the study's ability to capture temporal dynamics and draw strong causal conclusions regarding the relationship between *customer incivility*, *self-efficacy*, and *work engagement*. Secondly, the use of *self-report* instruments may introduce perceptual bias and *common method bias*. Thirdly, the study's scope, which is limited to a single organisation and a single industry sector, restricts the generalisability of the findings. Fourth, the research model only tested *self-efficacy* as a moderator, meaning that other relevant psychological and organisational variables were not accommodated. Fifth, the absence of a qualitative approach limits an in-depth understanding of employees' subjective experiences. Future research is recommended to use a longitudinal or *mixed-methods* design, expand the research context, and test additional variables to gain a more comprehensive understanding.

Conclusion

The conclusions that can be drawn from the analysis of this study are as follows:

1. *Customer incivility* has a significant negative impact on *work engagement* among *frontline* staff at the Prama Sanur Beach Hotel in Bali. These results indicate that the higher the intensity of rude behaviour experienced by staff from customers, the lower the level of *work engagement* among *frontline* staff. Repeated instances of *customer incivility* have the potential to reduce staff energy, dedication and engagement in carrying out their duties.
2. *Self-efficacy* was not found to weaken the relationship between *customer incivility* and *work engagement* among *frontline* staff at the Prama Sanur Beach Hotel in Bali. The test results indicate that *self-efficacy* does not have a significant interactive effect in either weakening or strengthening the negative influence of *customer incivility* on *work engagement*. These findings suggest that employees' level of self-confidence in their abilities has not yet been able to act as a protective factor in reducing the negative impact of rude customer behaviour on work engagement.

Recommendations

The recommendations that can be made based on the results of this study are as follows:

1. The most prevalent form of *customer incivility*, and the one with the greatest impact on reducing *frontline* staff's *work engagement*, is demeaning verbal behaviour, such as speaking in a raised tone, a tendency to blame staff for issues that are not their responsibility, and treatment that conveys a lack of appreciation for staff competence. Management is advised to prioritise strengthening employees' psychological resilience through customer service training based on emotional management, which includes training in emotional control and regulation in high-pressure service situations, training in assertive and effective communication when dealing with guest complaints and

conflicts, and training in adaptive stress management strategies, such as constructive problem-solving, self-calming techniques, and scheduling short breaks during working hours. It is hoped that such training will boost employees' self-confidence in dealing with service pressures, enabling them to maintain optimal work engagement, whilst also strengthening *supervisors'* roles in providing consistent psychological support. Providing access to counselling services and reinforcing organisational policies that protect employees from rude customer behaviour are considered vital for sustaining employees' *work engagement* within a high-intensity service environment.

2. Enhancing the *self-efficacy* of *frontline* staff is a relevant strategic step in efforts to strengthen employees' psychological resilience when dealing with *customer incivility* during service interactions. Although research findings indicate that *self-efficacy* does not act as a significant moderating variable, bolstering self-confidence remains crucial as a personal resource that supports individuals' readiness to cope with the social and emotional demands of their work. Management must ensure that *frontline* staff feel tangible organisational support when dealing with un , so that they possess a stronger sense of self-confidence in managing challenging work situations. Such support can be demonstrated through the provision of appreciation or recognition for good service performance, which contributes to enhancing employees' sense of competence and self-worth. Such reinforcement can help employees maintain emotional stability and professionalism in complex service situations. Management is also advised to assist employees in developing systematic strategies for handling *customer incivility*, including planning for assertive communication, efforts to uphold professional standards, and clear, structured procedures for resolving conflicts between employees and customers. The provision of clear operational guidelines and a safe incident reporting mechanism can enhance employees' psychological sense of security at work. The implementation of these measures is expected to maintain employees' psychological stability and sustain levels of *work engagement* within a high-intensity service environment. An integrated approach combining the strengthening of human resources and organisational support is key to minimising the negative impact of customer incivility more effectively.
3. Future research is encouraged to consider the inclusion of other variables based on the *Job Demands–Resources (JD-R)* framework, including additional *job demands* such as emotional workload, role conflict and time pressure, as well as *job resources* such as supervisor support, role clarity and organisational justice, which may influence *work engagement*. Future research could also examine other outcome variables influenced by *customer incivility*, such as emotional exhaustion, job satisfaction, service performance, and turnover intention, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of job demands and resources. It is also recommended that future research expand its scope beyond *frontline* staff at the Prama Sanur Beach Hotel in Bali, or consider alternative research locations to provide a broader perspective.

REFERENCES

- Al Halbusi, Al-Sulaiti, Khalid; AlAbri, Salem; Al-Sulaiti, Ibrahim (2023) : Individual and psychological factors influencing hotel employee's work engagement: The contingent role of self-efficacy, *Cogent Business & Management*, ISSN 2331-1975, Taylor & Francis, Abingdon, Vol. 10, Iss. 3, pp. 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2254914>
- Al Halbusi, H., Williams, K., Akosile, A., & Ramayah, T. (2023). Individual and psychological factors influencing hotel employees' work engagement: The contingent role of self-efficacy. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), 2254914. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2254914> .
- Alola, U. V., Avci, T., & Öztüren, A. (2019). Customer incivility and employees' outcomes in the hotel: Testing the mediating role of emotional exhaustion. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 29, 9–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2018.10.004> .
- Alqhaiwi, Z. O., Gunasekara, A., Luu, T., & Djurkovic, N. (2024). When incivility begets incivility among hotel employees: The moderating effects of trait mindfulness and negative affect. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 123, Article 103918. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2024.103918> .
- Alsadaan, N., Ramadan, O. M. E., & Alqahtani, M. (2024). From incivility to outcomes: Tracing the effects of nursing incivility on nurse well-being, patient engagement, and health outcomes. *BMC Nursing*, 23, 325. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-024-01996-9>.
- Andersson, L. M., & Pearson, C. M. (1999). The spiraling effect of incivility in the workplace. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(3), 452–471. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1999.2202131>
- Andersson, L. M., & Pearson, C. M. (1999). Tit for tat? The spiraling effect of incivility in the workplace. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(3), 452–471. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1999.2202131>.
- Auh, S., Menguc, B., Thompson, F. M., & Uslu, A. (2024). Conflict-solving as a mediator between customer incivility and service performance. *The Service Industries Journal*, 44(5–6), 342–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2022.2094916> .
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2007). The Job Demands-Resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309–328. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940710733115> .
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2007). The Job Demands–Resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309–328. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940710733115> .
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2017). Job demands–resources theory: Taking stock and looking forward. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 22(3), 273–285. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000056> .
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2017). Job demands–resources theory: Taking stock and looking forward. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 22(3), 273–285. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000056>.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York: W.H. Freeman.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. W. H. Freeman.
- Bani-Melhem, S., Abukhait, R. M., Shamsudin, F. M., & West, M. (2022). Customer incivility and customer problem-solving behaviour in frontline employees: Testing a

- moderated mediation model. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 33(3–4), 278–296. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2020.1842187> .
- Bernthal, P., Wellins, R. S., & Phelps, M. (2005). *Employee engagement: The key to realizing competitive advantage*. Development Dimensions International.
- Boukis, A., Koritos, C., da Mota, M. M., & Papastathopoulos, A. (2023). Customer incivility as an identity threat for frontline employees: The mitigating role of organizational rewards. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 98, 103028.
- Boukis, A., Koritos, C., Papastathopoulos, A., & Buhalis, D. (2023). Customer incivility as an identity threat for frontline employees: The mitigating role of organizational rewards. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 100, Article 103555. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2023.103555>.
- Cash, R. E., White-Mills, K., Crowe, R. P., Rivard, M. K., & Panchal, A. R. (2019). Workplace incivility among nationally certified EMS professionals and associations with workforce-reducing factors and organizational culture. *Prehospital Emergency Care*, 23(3), 346–355. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10903127.2018.1502383>.
- Cheng, P., Zhang, J., & Wang, Z. (2024). Predicting frontline employees' emotional labor after customer incivility: The role of job passion. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 119, 103678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104178> .
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE.
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499–512.
- Dewi, A. K., Susanti, E. D., Asmi, Z. A., & Dwiyantri, R. (2019, April 27). The effect of workplace incivility on emotional exhaustion in frontline employees at Sambel Layah Corporation Purbalingga. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Seminar on Psychology: Empowerment of Human Resources Local Wisdom in a Psychological Perspective Towards Industrial Revolution 4.0* (pp. 73–79).
- Duan, W., Kong, Y., Chen, Z., & Mu, W. (2023). COVID-19-induced social exclusion and quality of life among Chinese adolescents in the context of family education: The mediating role of perceived control. *Educational Psychology*, 43(10), 1488–1505.
- Farisi, M. I., Suryani, R., & Tanjung, H. (2024). The Influence of Affective Commitment on Work Engagement in Public Sector Organizations. *Ekonomi dan Manajemen (EJM)*, 21(1), 85–95. <https://www.ecojoin.org/index.php/EJM/article/view/1817>.
- Federman, Brad. (2009). *Employee Engagement A Roadmap for Creating Profits, Optimizing Performance, and Increasing Loyalty*. Jossey-Bass business and management series.
- Gaan, N., & Shin, Y. (2023). Supervisor incivility and frontline employees' performance amid the COVID-19 pandemic: A multilevel moderated mediation analysis. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 73, 103347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2023.103347> .
- Gopalan, M., Pattusamy, M., & Hassan, Z. (2021). Linking family incivility to workplace incivility: Mediating role of negative emotions and moderating role of self-efficacy for emotional regulation. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*, 8(1), 90–112.
- Gu Y, Wang C and Ma J (2024) Explaining the negative effects of workplace incivility on family lives: a moderated mediation model of surface acting and resource-providing variables. *Front. Psychol.* 15:1409144. <http://doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1409144> .

- Guo, G., Jia, Y., Mu, W., & Wang, T. (2022). Workplace incivility and work engagement: The mediating role of job insecurity and the moderating role of self-perceived employability. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 43(1), 192–205.
- Guppy JH, Widlund H, Munro R, Price J. (2024) Incivility in healthcare: the impact of poor communication. *BMJ Leader*; 8:83-87.
- Gustiawan, D., Noermijati, Aisjah, S., & Indrawati, N. K. (2023). Customer incivility, employee emotional exhaustion, and job embeddedness relationship in the Indonesian hospitality sector: The socio-economic status perspective. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 9(1), 2178613. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2178613> .
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2022). *Multivariate data analysis* (8th ed.). Cengage.
- Hewitt, D. (2008), *Understanding Effective Learning: Strategies for The Classroom*. New York: The McGraw-Hill Companies. <http://docshare03.docshare.tips/files/16043/160434792.pdf>.
- Hur, W. M., Moon, T. W., & Jun, J. K. (2023). Customer incivility and employee work engagement: The role of personal resources. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 110, 103451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2023.103451> .
- Hur, W. M., Shin, Y., & Shin, G. (2022). Daily relationships between customer incivility, organizational control, self-efficacy, and service performance. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 69, Article 103092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103092>.
- Hur, W.M., Moon, T.W., & Han, S.J. (2023). Co-worker and customer incivility on employee well-being: Roles of helplessness, social support at work and psychological detachment. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 56, 443-453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2023.07.009>.
- Hur, W.-M., Shin, Y., & Shin, G. (2022). Daily relationships between customer incivility, organizational control, self-efficacy, and service performance. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 69, 103092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103092> .
- Jang, J., & Juliana. (2020). Pengaruh Persepsi Dukungan Organisasi Dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Komitmen Kerja Dan Organizational Citizenship Behavior Generasi Milenial Di Industri Pendidikan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen, Ekonomi, Dan Akuntansi*, 4(1), 141–160.
- Kahn, W. A. (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692–724.
- Karatepe, O. M. (2013). High-performance work practices, work social support and their effects on job embeddedness and turnover intentions. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 25(6), 903–921. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-06-2012-0097>.
- Kim, H., & Qu, H. (2019). The effects of experienced customer incivility on employees' behavior toward customers and coworkers. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 43(1), 58–77. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348018764583>
- Kim, H., & Ra, Y.-A. (2022). Effect of academic self-efficacy and career decision level on career preparation behavior of South Korean college students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(20), 13705. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192013705>.

- Kristiana, I. F., Prasetyo, A. R., & Wulandari, D. (2019). Validitas dan reliabilitas Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) versi Indonesia. *Jurnal Psikologi Udayana*, 6(2), 223–232. <https://doi.org/10.24843/JPU.2019.v06.i02.p09> .
- Kuncoro, A. (2021). *Psikologi Pendidikan: Teori dan Aplikasi dalam Pembelajaran*. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
- Kuriakose, A., Pillai, P. R., & Nair, V. (2023). Co-worker and customer incivility on employee well-being in the hospitality industry: The mediating role of helplessness and moderating role of social support and psychological detachment. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 56, 194–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2023.07.009> .
- Lea, S. E. G., Tarpy, R. M., & Webley, P. (1992). *The individual in the economy: A textbook of economic psychology*. Cambridge University Press.
- Leiter, M. P., & Bakker, A. B. (2010). Work engagement: Introduction. In A. B. Bakker & M. P. Leiter (Eds.), *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research* (pp. 1–9). Psychology Press.
- Lin, Y., Zhang, C., & Li, X. (2023). Customer mistreatment and employee engagement: A moderated mediation model. *Journal of Business Research*, 157, 113604.
- Lockwood, N. R. (2005). Talent management: Driver for organizational success. *HRMagazine*, 50(6), 1–11. [https://www.shrm.org/hr-today/trends-and-forecasting/special-reports-and-expert-views/Documents/Talent Management.pdf](https://www.shrm.org/hr-today/trends-and-forecasting/special-reports-and-expert-views/Documents/Talent%20Management.pdf).
- Lockwood, N. R. (2007). *Leveraging employee engagement for competitive advantage*. Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM).
- Luthans, F., Youssef, C. M., & Avolio, B. J. (2007). *Psychological capital: Developing the human competitive edge*. Oxford University Press.
- Madera, J. M. & Lee, L., (2019). Faking it or feeling it: The emotional displays of surface and deep acting on stress and engagement. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 31(4), 1744–1762. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-05-2018-0405>.
- Maharani, N. (2022). *Psikologi Pendidikan dan Perkembangan*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Makoto Fujii (2025) Bridging the missing link between customer incivility and service outcomes, *The Service Industries Journal*, 45:15-16, 1398-1420. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2025.2454944>.
- Mathur, A., Swarup, K., Agnihotri, D., Chaturvedi, P., & Tripathi, V. (2025). *Investigating employee acceptance of smart technologies through UTAUT model with self-efficacy as a mediator*. *International Journal of Innovation Science*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJIS-06-2024-0155>.
- Morrow, P. C., McElroy, J. C., & Scheibe, K. P. (2011). Work unit incivility, job satisfaction, and total quality management among transportation employees. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 14(6), 525–536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2011.06.004> .
- Morrow, P. C., McElroy, J. C., Stamper, C. L., & Wilson, M. A. (2011). The role of customer incivility and organizational support in predicting work outcomes. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 16(1), 26–37. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021712>.
- Mostafa, A. M. S. (2022). Customer incivility, work engagement and service-oriented citizenship behaviours in the hospitality industry. *Human Performance*, 35(6), 581–603.

- Pearson, C. M., Andersson, L. M., & Porath, C. L. (2000). Assessing and attacking workplace incivility. *Organizational Dynamics*, 29(2), 123–137.
- Pennings, H. J. M., van Bruggen, J. M. E., Chen, H. C., & van der Schaaf, M. F., (2025). Evolving health professions educators' work engagement in teaching while combining roles in an academic medical center. *BMC Medical Education*, 25(1), 1035. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-025-07628-3>.
- Pennings, H. J. M., van der Velde, D., Hommel, B., & Oudejans, R. R. D. (2025). Calibration accuracy of general and task-specific self-efficacy in a military training simulator. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, 1459993. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1459993>.
- Piramanayagam, S., Asthaabhipsa rout, and Jyothi mallya (2025). Customer incivility in hospitality: insights from existing literature and pathways for future research. *Cogent Business & Management*, 12(1), 2513627. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2025.2513627>.
- Rahyuda, I. K. (2020). *Metode penelitian bisnis: Based of the research pyramid* (Edisi 2020). Denpasar: CV Sastra Utama.
- Robinson, D., Perryman, S. and Hayday, S. (2004). The Drivers of Employee Engagement. IES Report 408: Institute for Employment Studies.
- Sabila S & Umi A (2025). Work Engagement Pada Karyawan: Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Information System, Applied, Management, Accounting and Research*. Vol.9No.3(2025), Pp.1187-1195. <http://doi:10.52362/jisamar.v9i3.1983>.
- Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2023). *Research methods for business students* (9th ed.). Pearson.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2003). *Utrecht Work Engagement Scale: Preliminary manual*. Utrecht University.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement: A multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(3), 293–315. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.248>.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2010). Defining and measuring work engagement: Bringing clarity to the concept. In A. B. Bakker & M. P. Leiter (Eds.), *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research* (pp. 10–24). Psychology Press.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Taris, T. W. (2014). A critical review of the Job Demands-Resources Model: Implications for improving work and health. In Bauer & Hämmig (Eds.), *Bridging Occupational, Organizational and Public Health* (pp. 43-68). Springer.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., & Salanova, M. (2006). The measurement of work engagement with a short questionnaire: A cross-national study. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 66(4), 701–716. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164405282471>.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Martínez, I. M., Pinto, A. M., Salanova, M., & Bakker, A. B. (2002). Burnout and engagement in university students: A cross-national study. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 33(5), 464–48.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B. (2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two-sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3(1), 71–92.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Taris, T. W., & Van Rhenen, W. (2008). Workaholism, burnout and engagement: three of a kind or three different kinds of employee wellbeing. *Applied Psychology-An International Review*, 57(2), 173-203.

- Schmidt, F. A. (2004). *Employee engagement and commitment*. Society for Human Resource Management.
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2020). Motivation and social-emotional learning: Theory, research, and practice. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2020). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach* (8th ed.). Wiley.
- Savigo, A. F. D., Nurhasanah, S., & Febriani, R. (2023). The influence of work-life balance on job satisfaction with burnout as an intervening variable. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis dan Kewirausahaan (Jamanika)*, 3(3), 238–248. <https://doi.org/10.22219/jamanika.v3i03.29582>
- Shahzad, F., Ali, S., Hussain, I., Sun, L., Wang, C. Ahmad (2023) F. The Impact of Customer Incivility and Its Consequences on Hotel Employees: Mediating Role of Employees' Emotional Exhaustion. *Sustainability*, 15, 15211. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152115211> .
- Shahzad, F., Ali, S., Hussain, I., Sun, L., Wang, C., & Ahmad, F. (2023). The impact of customer incivility and its consequences on hotel employees: Mediating role of employees' emotional exhaustion. *Sustainability*, 15(21), 15211. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152115211>.
- Shao, R., & Skarlicki, D. P. (2014). Service employees' reactions to mistreatment by customers: A comparison between North America and East Asia. *Personnel Psychology*, 67(1), 23–59. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12021>.
- Shin, G., Hur, W.-M., & Shin, Y. (2023). Does person–job fit buffer employees from rumination about customer incivility?. *Current Psychology*, 42, 15503–15518. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-023-04930-5>.
- Sliter, M., Jex, S., Wolford, K., & McInerney, J. (2010). How rude! Emotional labor as a mediator between customer incivility and employee outcomes. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 15(4), 468–481. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0020723>.
- Sliter, M., Sliter, K., & Jex, S. (2012). The employee as a punching bag: The effect of multiple sources of incivility on employee withdrawal behavior and sales performance. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 33(1), 121–139. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.767> .
- Smythe, J. (2007). Employee engagement – its real essence: ... and how it helped to transform a top-four UK bank. *Human Resource Management International Digest*, 15(7), 11–13. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09670730710830405>.
- Solimun, Adji Achmad Rinaldo Fernandes, & Nurjannah. (2017). *Metode Statistika Multivariat: Pemodelan Persamaan Struktural (SEM) Pendekatan WarpPLS*. UB Press.(JED), 6(1), 223–236. <https://doi.org/10.20414/jed.v6i1.9395>.
- Sugiyono. (2019). *Metode penelitian kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D* (Edisi ke-2, Cetakan ke-1). Bandung: Alfabeta. ISBN: 9786022895336.
- Sugiyono. (2020). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Syarifah, I. (2021). *Manajemen sumber daya manusia*. CV Eureka Media Aksara.
- Sypniewska Barbara, Małgorzata Baran, Monika Kłos (2023). Work engagement and employee satisfaction in the practice of sustainable human resource management – based on the study of Polish employees. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal* (2023) 19:1069–1100 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-023-00834-9> .
- Talsma, K., Schüz, B., Schwarzer, R., & Norris, K. (2019). I believe, therefore I achieve (and vice versa): A meta-analytic cross-lagged panel analysis of self-efficacy and

- academic performance. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 73, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2019.04.006>.
- Tam, D. U. (2023). Customer mistreatment and employees' extra-role performance: A goal failure perspective. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science – Economics and Business Administration*, 13(2), 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.46223/HCMCOUJS.econ.en.13.2.2459.2023>.
- Tam, D. U. (2025). The effects of experienced customer incivility on employees' job performance: The mediating role of ego depletion and moderating role of mindfulness. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQSS-01-2025-0012>.
- Tam, D. U., & Trang, N. T. M. (2023). Linking workplace incivility and frontline employees' subjective well-being: The role of work-home enrichment and coping strategies. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 16(3), 696–715. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJBA-05-2022-0203>.
- Tam, D. U., & Trang, N. T. M. (2024). Customer and supervisor incivility, psychological distress, and job performance among airport frontline employees: The moderating role of mindfulness. *Service Business*, 18(3), 395–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11628-024-00565-z>.
- Truss, C., Soane, E., Edwards, C., Wisdom, K., Croll, A., & Burnett, J. (2006). *Working life: Employee attitudes and engagement 2006*. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.
- Usher, E. L., & Pajares, F. (2019). Sources of self-efficacy in school: Critical review of the literature. *Review of Educational Research*.
- Wang, C.H., & Chen, H.T. (2020). Relationships among workplace incivility, work engagement and job performance. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 3(4), 415-429. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-09-2019-0105>.
- Wang, M., & Chen, L. (2020). Relationships among workplace incivility, work engagement and job performance. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 3(4), 415–432. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-09-2019-0103>.
- Weiss, H. M., & Cropanzano, R. (1996). Affective events theory: A theoretical discussion of the structure, causes and consequences of affective experiences at work. In B. M. Staw & L. L. Cummings (Eds.), *Research in organizational behavior* (Vol. 18, pp. 1–74). JAI Press.
- Wellins, R., & Concelman, J. (2005). *Creating a culture for engagement*. *Workforce Performance Solutions*. Retrieved from <https://www.ddiworld.com>.
- Widyadana, S., & Hendarsjah, H. (2024). Pengaruh customer incivility terhadap turnover intention, job embeddedness dan dimediasi oleh emotional exhaustion. *Journal of Economic, Bussines and Accounting (COSTING)*, 7(4), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.31539/costing.v7i5.11274>.
- Wisesa, I. M. S., & Rahyuda, A. G. (2024). Does self-efficacy moderate the effect of customer incivility on work engagement?. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, XVII(03), 281–292. <https://doi.org/10.21632/irjbs.17.3.281-292>.
- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2009). Work engagement and financial returns: A diary study on the role of job and personal resources. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 82(1), 183–200. <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317908X285633>.

- Yon, D. J. (2022). Rude customers and service performance: Roles of motivation and personality. *The Service Industries Journal*, 42(1-2), 81-106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2020.1826453> .
- Zeithaml, V. A., Bitner, M. J., & Gremler, D. D. (2018). *Services marketing: Integrating customer focus across the firm* (7th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Education.